

Section 1: Consent Questions

EXPLANATORY STATEMENT

(Developers and Reporters)

Project ID: 30660

Project title: Improving Human-Centric Software Defect Evaluation, Reporting, and Fixing

Chief Investigator's name:

Prof John Grundy, Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity

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Student Investigator:

Vedant Chauhan, Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity

Email: vedant.chauhan@monash.edu

You are invited to take part in this study. Please read this explanatory statement in full before deciding to participate in this study. If you would like further information regarding any aspect of this study, you are encouraged to contact the researchers via the email address listed above.

What does the research involve?

As part of the PhD project funded by Prof John Grundy's ARC Laureate Fellowship, we are researching new approaches to improve human-centric defect reporting and fixing in open-source and closed-source environments. The

field of software engineering consists of working software and the associated defects with that software. The research involves defects arising from the human-centric aspects such as personality, ethnicity, culture, diverse age, gender, educational background, accessibility, usability etc., in the software applications. The subjective nature of these defects creates them challenging to capture. The project aims to find new strategies and techniques to capture these human-centric defects and improve software development and reporting processes.

This study will look at current developers and reporters working with software systems and experiencing human-centric defects. We are particularly interested in developers' and reporters' perceptions of defects in software applications related to human-centric aspects such as users with different age groups, users with diverse cultural backgrounds, users with low language proficiency levels, users with physical and mental challenges, users with less experience in technology, and so on. In addition, we are interested in finding the challenges with team climate, organisations impact, and the current defect reporting tools in accommodating the human-centric defects and strategies which can be applied to solve these problems.

As part of this study, you will be asked to answer an online survey about taking into account various human-centric defects during software development and maintenance. The survey should take around 15-20 minutes to complete.

We are also seeking to find some survey respondents who might be willing to undertake a Zoom or face-to-face interview to learn more about their experiences. This interview is likely to take around 20-30 minutes. This is optional, and we will only seek to interview a representative cross-section of willing respondents.

Why were you chosen for this research?

You are invited to the research because you represent the active group working on defect reporting and fixing. In addition, you're a professional contact of the researchers; you have been sent an invitation by email or have clicked on one of our survey advertisements. As a developer and reporter, we believe you can provide significant insight on this topic.

For Amazon Mechanical Turk Workforce, you are invited to the surveys to represent the working group of developers and reporters in defect reporting and fixing. For each survey response, we will pay 6.40 USD i.e. 8.92 AUD* (at the time (21st Feb 2022) exchange rate: 1 USD = 1.39 AUD *subjected to change based on the currency exchange value).

Consenting to participate in the project and withdrawing from the research Survey. You were informed about this study via an email, an advertisement on LinkedIn, or a personal contact to one of our research team members. The information presented in the advertisement briefly highlights the purpose of this study and a URL to access the online survey. Additionally, at the start of the online survey, there is an explanatory statement and a statement of consent. If you agree to participate in this study, please check the consent box to indicate that you have read the explanatory statement, understand the purpose and method of the study, and are ready to answer the online survey.

You can withdraw participation from the online survey at any time during data collection. After you submit your online survey response, the data will be anonymised with no link to your personal details. Consequently, withdrawing after data has been anonymised will not be possible. If you choose not to participate but are still interested in the outcome, you can inform the researchers, and they will send you a report of the findings once available.

Interview. If you indicate a willingness to be interviewed by one of the team members via Zoom or face-to-face, we will email you a statement of the purpose of the interview and a consent form. After signing and returning the consent form to us via email, we will schedule an interview with you. At any time before or during the interview, you can withdraw participation, and we will discard all of your partial interview data. In addition, after the interview, we will de-identify your interview responses, and consequently, withdrawing after three days, this interview data has been anonymised will not be possible.

Possible benefits and risks to participants

Survey. Participation in this study is voluntary. No reward is given for participation. However, your valuable feedback is essential to identify the area of

improvement in reporting and to fix the human-centric defects in software systems.

Interview. Participation in this study is voluntary. If you decide to participate in the interview process, as a token of appreciation for your valuable time you will receive one \$20 gift card at the conclusion of the interview process. Options for the gift card include - Coles, Myer, iTunes, and Amazon, please let the interviewer know your preference.

Confidentiality

Survey. The online survey will not ask for any identifying information, except for an email address if you indicate you are willing to be interviewed or if you wish to be sent a report on the study at its conclusion.

Your responses will be detached from your email address if supplied, and in that way, the responses will be completely anonymous. You can decide to withdraw or not to participate at any point during data collection. However, once you send us through your survey responses and those have already been anonymised, there is no way to get back the individual responses, and such withdrawal will not be possible during the data analysis phase. Only the researchers will store and retain the data and will not be shared with any third party.

Interview. If you indicate a willingness to be interviewed by one of the team members via Zoom or face-to-face, and we invite you to participate in a Zoom interview, one of the researchers will record the interview with your permission or otherwise take notes during the interview. After the interview, the researcher will transcribe and anonymise your interview responses and destroy any recording. Audio recordings will be transcribed by third party professional services. This company will not be provided with full names, contact details or other identifying information. You can decide to withdraw or not to participate at any point before or during the interview. However, once we have anonymised your interview notes after three days, there is no way to get back the individual responses, and such withdrawing will not be possible during the data analysis phase. Only the researchers will store and retain the data and will not be shared with any third party.

Storage of data

Survey. The survey data will be stored securely in the Qualtrics online survey tool, on a secure Monash server, and the researcher's computer, during different phases of data collection, analysis and write-up. All of these systems and computers are protected by passwords and cannot be accessed by others. Qualtrics survey data will be deleted at the survey close after download to a secure Monash server. All study data will be destroyed five years past the study.

Interview. The Zoom recording will be stored in the Zoom conference system before downloading to a secure Monash server, then deleted from Zoom. The audio recording transcription will be handled by third party service whose security and privacy policies are industry standard. This company will not be provided any sensitive information. After transcription of the interview, the recording will be deleted from Zoom and the transcription service.

Use of data for other purposes

The data collected for this study may be used for other studies within five years only if relevant. In case of re-use, the data will still be in anonymised form.

Results

The results of this study will be published in peer-reviewed academic conferences and/or journals and maybe summarised at relevant industry workshops. A copy of the final report will be sent to the participants on request.

Complaints

Should you have any concerns or complaints about the conduct of the project, you are welcome to contact the Executive Officer, Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC):

Executive Officer
Monash University
Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC)
Room 111, Chancellery Building D,
26 Sports Walk, Clayton Campus
Research Office Monash University VIC 3800
Tel: +61 3 9905 2052

Email: muhrec@monash.edu

Fax: +61 3 9905 3831

Thank you,

ARC Laureate Professor John Grundy

CONSENT FORM

(Developers and Reporters)

Project ID: 30660

Project title: Improving Human-Centric Software Defect Evaluation, Reporting, and Fixing

Chief Investigator's name:

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Email: john.grundy@monash.edu

Dr Hourieh Khalajzadeh, Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity

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Dr Chetan Arora, School of Info Technology, Deakin University

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Student Investigator:

Vedant Chauhan, Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity

Email: vedant.chauhan@monash.edu

I have been asked to take part in the Monash University research project specified above. I hereby consent to participate in this project.

I consent to the following (please select each box that you consent/agree with):

- I have read and understood the Explanatory Statement
- I agree to answer an online survey
- The data that I provide during this research may be used by the investigators in future research projects
- I certify that all the information above is correct. I understand that by clicking the 'Next' button below is giving my consent to participate in the research

study and is the equivalent of signing a consent form.

Section 2: Demographics

In which country do you currently reside?

Age:

Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / gender diverse
- My gender identity isn't listed. I identify as:
- Prefer not to say

Highest Education:

- Some high school credit, no diploma, or the equivalent
- High school graduate, diploma, or the equivalent
- Some college credit, no degree
- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Associate degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Professional degree
- Doctorate degree
- Other:

If you are currently a student or have completed a college degree, please specify your field(s) of study:

- Computer Science
- Information Technology
- Computer Engineering
- Information Systems
- Architecture
- Arts and Humanities
- Chemical Engineering
- Biology
- Business
- Other:

Current Role:

- Project Management
- Software Architect
- Software Engineer/Software Developer/Programmer
- Delivery Engineer/Lead
- User interface designer/UX
- Test Engineer/Tester/Quality Assurance
- Security Engineer/Consultant
- Business Analyst
- Operations
- Other:

Total Experience:

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you assess your proficiency in each of the following technical skills (1 being a beginner or having no experience and 5 being an expert)?

	1	2	3	4	5
Web Development	<input type="radio"/>				
Mobile Development	<input type="radio"/>				
Software testing	<input type="radio"/>				
Test Automation	<input type="radio"/>				
Programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Database Management	<input type="radio"/>				
System Administration	<input type="radio"/>				
UX/usability/user interface	<input type="radio"/>				
Security/Secure code practices	<input type="radio"/>				

What is your field of work?

- Information Technology
- IT-Finance
- IT-Manufacturing
- IT-Spatial
- IT-Government
- IT-Gaming
- IT-Healthcare
- IT-Telecommunications
- Other

Section 3: Human-centric defects

You can choose to fill either of the next section or both based on your expertise:

- Developer (Individuals working on fixing the defects)
- Reporter (Individuals who are reporting defects i.e. Tester, End-user, etc.)

Section 3a: Developer Questions

Total-experience in development:

Do you have any experience in testing/reporting issues?

Section 3a: Developer - Human-centric defects

What do you think human-centric defects mean?

Our definition: Human-centric design involves designing and developing software by keeping user needs at the forefront of the process. Decisions are taken on how users will perform, perceive tasks instead of asking users to adjust. Users can have different gender, languages, culture, disabilities, and so on. Due to this subjective nature of differences, the problems can vary for distinct users, resulting in defects in the application called human-centric

defects.

Below are some examples of human-centric defects:

Example1: While booking an Uber, the option to include the child seat is very confusing and requires extra effort from the user to get it included in their ride. For a regular user, this is not an issue. However, for a parent with a child, this instantly becomes a human-centric defect. The defect also falls under the domain of functional defect.

Example2: An individual with colour blindness perceives a website differently than a regular user. This defect also falls under the domain of usability defects.

Did you ever experience human-centric defects during the software development process?

Please provide any examples you encountered in the development process.

Yes

No

What type of defect category consisted of more human-centric defects during development?

	Never	Sometimes	Seldom	Always
Functional	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Security	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Usability

Compatibility

What characteristics do you look for while identifying issues? Can the same be applied to human-centric defects?

Sometimes experience can play a crucial role in fixing defects. According to you, does experience also play an essential role in fixing human-centric defects? Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Individuals at different geographic locations can add some delays in fixing defects. Can offshore resources, or time zone differences also delay the fixing of human-centric defects? Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Does the size of an organisation impact the fixing of human-centric defects? In other words, if the size of an organization is smaller or bigger, can it lead to fixing human-centric defects faster or slower?

Team climate is the employee's shared perception of organisational events, practices, and procedures (Anderson & West, 1998). Does team climate impact the fixing of defects, specifically human-centric defects?

Section 3a: Developer - Defect Reporting tools

Experience using defect reporting tools:

- 0-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-8 years
- 9+ years

Which tool do you have previous experience in? (tick all that apply)

- Bugzilla
-

- JIRA
- Trello
- Mantis
- Trac
- Zendesk
- Redmine
- Servicenow
- Asana
- Backlog
- Monday.com
- Zoho Bug tracker
- BugHerd
- Bugsnag
- Other:

According to you, what challenges does the defect reporting tools provide while addressing human-centric defects?

What ideas can you recommend to better address human-centric defects in defect reporting tools?

Below are the characteristics which can be seen on a general defect form; for e.g. Bugzilla, JIRA, etc. On a scale of 1 to 5, which characteristics can be the most significant for fixing human-centric defects (1 being the least important and 5 being the most important)?

	1	2	3	4	5
Severity of the issue	<input type="radio"/>				
Priority of the issue	<input type="radio"/>				
Hardware	<input type="radio"/>				
OS	<input type="radio"/>				
Version	<input type="radio"/>				
Product/Component	<input type="radio"/>				
Bug Description	<input type="radio"/>				
Expected behaviour	<input type="radio"/>				
Observed behaviour	<input type="radio"/>				
Steps to Reproduce	<input type="radio"/>				
Impact	<input type="radio"/>				
Assumed cause	<input type="radio"/>				
Solution proposal	<input type="radio"/>				
Supplementary Information (screenshots, stack traces, URL, links, videos)	<input type="radio"/>				

Does the experience in using defect reporting tools influence the quality of defect reports?

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Which below approach is an ideal location to maintain human-centric defects?
Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

- Central database with all other functional, performance, security defects.

- Separate database containing only human-centric defects.

In your experience, how are the defects assigned to developers?
Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Can the same reasoning be applied to human-centric defects?

- the person with the more general experience, or

- the person with more specific module/project experience

Do the recommendations of past similar defects allow fixing them faster?
For example, previous similar defects containing commit history, comments, descriptions, severity rating, and so on.

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Can the same reasoning be applied to human-centric defects?

Yes

No

Section 3b: Reporter Questions

Total-experience in reporting/testing:

Do you have any experience in software development?

Section 3b: Reporter - Human-centric defects

What do you think human-centric defects mean?

Our definition: Human-centric design involves designing and developing software by keeping user needs at the forefront of the process. Decisions are taken on how users will perform, perceive tasks instead of asking users to adjust. Users can have different gender, languages, culture, disabilities, and so on. Due to this subjective nature of differences, the problems can vary for distinct users, resulting in defects in the application called human-centric defects.

Below are some examples of human-centric defects:

Example1: While booking an Uber, the option to include the child seat is very confusing and requires extra effort from the user to get it included in their ride. For a regular user, this is not an issue. However, for a parent with a child, this instantly becomes a human-centric defect. The defect also falls under the domain of functional defect.

Example2: An individual with colour blindness perceives a website differently than a regular user. This defect also falls under the domain of usability defects.

Did you ever experience human-centric defects during the software development and test process?

Please provide any examples you encountered in the development process.

Yes

No

What type of defect category consisted of more human-centric defects during

development?

	Never	Sometimes	Seldom	Always
Functional	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Performance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Security	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compatibility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What characteristics do you look for while identifying issues? Can the same be applied to human-centric defects?

Sometimes experience can play a crucial role in defects. According to you, does experience also play an essential role in reporting human-centric defects?

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Individuals at different geographic locations can add some delays in finding

defects. Can offshore resources, or time zone differences also delay the finding of human-centric defects?

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Does the size of an organisation impact the finding of human-centric defects? In other words, if the size of an organization is smaller or bigger, can it lead to finding human-centric defects faster or slower?

Team climate is the employee's shared perception of organisational events, practices, and procedures (Anderson & West, 1998). Does team climate impact the finding of defects, specifically human-centric defects?

Section 3b: Reporter - Defect Reporting tools

Experience using defect reporting tools:

- 0-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-8 years
- 9+ years

Which tool do you have previous experience in? (tick all that apply)

- Bugzilla
- JIRA
- Trello
- Mantis
- Trac
- Zendesk
- Redmine
- Servicenow
- Asana
- Backlog
- Monday.com
- Zoho Bug tracker
- BugHerd
- Bugsnag
- Other:

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Priority of the issue	<input type="radio"/>				
Hardware	<input type="radio"/>				
OS	<input type="radio"/>				
Version	<input type="radio"/>				
Product/Component	<input type="radio"/>				
Bug Description	<input type="radio"/>				
Expected behaviour	<input type="radio"/>				
Observed behaviour	<input type="radio"/>				
Steps to Reproduce	<input type="radio"/>				
Impact	<input type="radio"/>				
Assumed cause	<input type="radio"/>				
Solution proposal	<input type="radio"/>				
Supplementary Information (screenshots, stack traces, URL, links, videos)	<input type="radio"/>				

Does the experience in using defect reporting tools influence the quality of

defect reports?

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Yes

No

Which below approach is an ideal location to maintain human-centric defects?

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Central database with all other functional, performance, security defects.

Separate database containing only human-centric defects.

In your experience, how are the defects assigned to developers or reporters?

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Can the same reasoning be applied to human-centric defects?

the person with the more general experience, or

- the person with more specific module/project experience

Do the recommendations of past similar defects allow fixing them faster?
For example, previous similar defects containing commit history, comments, descriptions, severity rating, and so on.

Please provide any reasoning behind your answer.

Can the same reasoning be applied to human-centric defects?

- Yes

- No

Section 4: Concluding Questions

Do you have any other feedback on issues related to reporting human-centric defects in software?

Would you be willing to consider being interviewed about some of these questions in more detail?

If yes, please provide your email address.

Yes

No

Do you want to be sent a report summarising the study findings at the conclusion of the study?

If yes, please provide your email address.

Yes

No